

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARticle Data (SPEARHEAD)

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable 8.3

Educational material on solar eruptions

EU's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme

Grant Agreement 101135044

UNIVERSITY
OF TURKU

Kiel University
Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel

UNIVERSITY
OF OULU

INAF
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE
DI ASTROFISICA

Lead Beneficiary	<i>University of Turku</i>
Authors	J. Gieseler, A. Papaioannou, R. Vainio, A. Afanasiev, M. Dumbovic, B. Heber, L. Annie John, J. Lang, E. Lavasa, A. Mishev, C. Ngom, S. Nyberg, C. Palmroos, A. Rouillard, P. Väisänen

Work Package	WP8: Dissemination
Task	Task 8.3
Deliverable	D8.3: Educational material on solar eruptions
Date for Deliverable	31 December 2025

Change Log				
Version	Date	Author(s)	Reason for Modification	Status
1	2025-12-22	Gieseler et al.	New Document	Submitted
2				

Dissemination Level	
Public	X
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Contents

Contents	3
List of Figures	4
List of Acronyms	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
Educational material on solar eruptions	7
1 Introduction	7
2 Special course held at UTU	7
3 Special course material	9
4 Conclusions and Outlook	9
Bibliography	11

List of Figures

1	Schedule of the MSc course held in May 2025 at UTU.	7
2	Student assessment of all course lectures and exercises held in May 2025 at UTU. The rating score is based on a five-point system, with 5 points corresponding to the highest rating.	8
3	Student assessment of the difficulty of all course session held in May 2025 at UTU. The rating score is based on a five-point system, with 1 point corresponding to "too easy" and 5 points "too difficult".	8

List of Acronyms

CAU	Christian-Albrechts-University Kiel
D	Deliverable
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
FD	Forbush Decrease
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
IRAP	Institute of Research in Astrophysics and Planetology
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
OH	Hvar Observatory
PDF	Portable Document Format
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOLER	Energetic Solar Eruptions: Data analysis and tools
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
UOULU	University of Oulu
UTU	University of Turku
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Within the SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) project, educational material based on its research results are provided and used in a Master-level course on solar eruptions which was held at University of Turku (UTU) in May 2025 (<https://spearhead-he.eu/msc-course/>). This document gives a summary of the course and describes the course material (lectures and exercises) that is publicly available for the scientific community.

1 Introduction

The **SPEARHEAD** project is not only creating scientific output, new data products or tools for the community, its results are also used in university education. As part of Work Package (WP) 8 (Dissemination), the project delivered educational material based on its research results and exploited them in a Master-level course on solar eruptions which took place at the **UTU** in May 2025. The course and the material used therein are outlined in this Deliverable (D) 8.3.

2 Special course held at **UTU**

The educational material described in this deliverable has been used in a MSc course titled "High-Energy Particles in the Heliosphere", which was held in hybrid mode at **UTU**. This 2-4-credit-point course was made up of eight teaching days (after an introduction on day 1) in May 2025. Each day would start with a lecture in the morning given by an expert on that topic and was intensified with a hands-on exercise session in the afternoon (see Fig. 1 for the schedule), in which the students would either solve connected calculation problems or work on the lecture topics using already available tools or those provided throughout **SPEARHEAD**.

Theme	Date	Lecture time	Tutorial time	Lecturers	Tutors
Introduction	2025-05-05	10–13		D. Morosan, R. Vainio	
Particle transport	2025-05-08	10–13	14–17	R. Vainio	J. Lang
Particle acceleration	2025-05-09	10–13	14–17	A. Afanasiev	J. Lang
Numerical simulations	2025-05-15	10–13	14–17	A. Afanasiev	S. Nyberg & L. Annie John
Space-borne observations	2025-05-16	10–13	14–17	R. Vainio & B. Heber	C. Palmroos & C. Ngom
Ground-based observations	2025-05-22	10–13	14–17	I. Usoskin/A. Mishev	P. Väisänen & J. Gieseler
GCR modulation / FDs	2025-05-23	10–13	14–17	M. Dumbovic	M. Dumbovic & J. Gieseler
Very high-energy SEP events	2025-05-27	10–13	14–17	A. Rouillard	E. Lavasa & J. Gieseler
Effects and statistical modelling	2025-05-28	10–13	14–17	A. Papaioannou	E. Lavasa & J. Gieseler

Figure 1: Schedule of the MSc course held in May 2025 at **UTU**.

The students enrolled at **UTU** received one credit point per two full course days, totalling in four credit points when attending all eight teaching days. The course was given in parallel to an additional course on energetic solar eruptions, organized by the European Union (EU) project Energetic Solar Eruptions: Data analysis and tools (**SOLER**), where the students could pick up additional lectures to gain up to six credit points in total. Students participating remotely received a participation certificate stating the number of credit points they would have been awarded at **UTU**. In total seven students participated in the course, five in person in Turku and two remotely. Following each teaching day, students were asked to evaluate both the lecture and the corresponding exercise session on a five-point scale, where 5 denotes the highest rating. As shown in Fig. 2, both components were received very positively: in each case, 62.2% of respondents awarded the highest grade (5), while the vast majority of the remaining ratings were 4 or 3. Only isolated low ratings were reported, indicating a consistently high level of satisfaction across sessions.

In addition, students were asked to assess the difficulty of the sessions relative to their prior knowledge, using a scale from 1 ("too easy") to 5 ("too difficult"). The results, presented in Fig. 3, show that most sessions were perceived as appropriately challenging. Specifically, 86.4% of responses fell within ratings 3 or 4, suggesting a well-balanced level of difficulty. Very few students rated the sessions as either too easy or too difficult, further indicating that the course content was well aligned with the participants' backgrounds.

Rate today's lecture!

[Copy chart](#)

37 responses

Rate today's exercise!

[Copy chart](#)

37 responses

Figure 2: Student assessment of all course lectures and exercises held in May 2025 at UTU. The rating score is based on a five-point system, with 5 points corresponding to the highest rating.

Rate the difficulty of today's sessions relative to your prior knowledge!

[Copy chart](#)

37 responses

Figure 3: Student assessment of the difficulty of all course session held in May 2025 at UTU. The rating score is based on a five-point system, with 1 point corresponding to "too easy" and 5 points "too difficult".

3 Special course material

All lectures and exercise sessions were conducted by members of the **SPEARHEAD** project partner institutes from Christian-Albrechts-University Kiel (**CAU**), Institute of Research in Astrophysics and Planetology (**IRAP**), National Observatory of Athens (**NOA**), Hvar Observatory (**OH**), University of Oulu (**UOULU**), and University of Turku (**UTU**). In detail, the responsible persons were:

- Day 1: Introduction
Rami Vainio and Diana Morosan (both **UTU**)
- Day 2: Particle transport
Lecture Rami Vainio (**UTU**), exercises Jaclyn T. Lang (**UTU**)
- Day 3: Particle acceleration
Lecture Alexandr Afanasiev (**UTU**), exercises Jaclyn T. Lang (**UTU**)
- Day 4: Numerical simulations
Lecture Alexandr Afanasiev (**UTU**), exercises Seve Nyberg and Lidiya Annie John (both **UTU**)
- Day 5: Space-borne observations
Lecture Rami Vainio (**UTU**) and Bernd Heber (**CAU**), exercises Christian Palmroos and Catherine Ngom (both **UTU**)
- Day 6: Ground-based observations
Lecture Alexander Mishev (**UOULU**), exercises Pauli Väisänen (**UOULU**) and Jan Gieseler (**UTU**)
- Day 7: Galactic Cosmic Ray (**GCR**) modulation and Forbush Decreases (**FDs**)
Lecture Mateja Dumbović (**OH**), exercises Mateja Dumbović (**OH**) and Jan Gieseler (**UTU**)
- Day 8: Very high-energy Solar Energetic Particle (**SEP**) events
Lecture Alexis P. Rouillard (**IRAP**) and Athanasios Papaioannou (**NOA**), exercises Eleni Lavasa (**NOA**) and Jan Gieseler (**UTU**)
- Day 9: Radiation effects and probabilistic modelling
Lecture Athanasios Papaioannou (**NOA**) and Rami Vainio (**UTU**), exercises Eleni Lavasa (**NOA**) and Jan Gieseler (**UTU**)

The slides and descriptions of all lectures and exercises of the MSc course are publicly made available as Portable Document Format (**PDF**) files at Zenodo, where a per-version citable Digital Object Identifier (**DOI**) is generated, allowing easy citation (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17951403](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17951403), Gieseler et al. 2025). All software tools needed for the exercises are either directly provided or their corresponding online repositories linked.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

The MSc course "**High-Energy Particles in the Heliosphere**" (<https://spearhead-he.eu/msc-course/>) within the **SPEARHEAD** project was successfully carried out in hybrid mode at **UTU** and online, allowing students and teachers from all over Europe to participate. The student assessment was quite favourable with an average of 4.35 out of 5 possible points for the lectures as well as the exercise sessions (cf. Fig. 2). All course materials developed by members of the consortium partners have been made publicly available to ensure long-term accessibility and reuse by the broader scientific and educational community. By releasing these resources openly, the materials can be continuously reused, adapted, and further developed, both as learning resources for students and as teaching material for instructors

integrating them into their own courses. This open-access approach fosters knowledge transfer beyond the lifetime of the project and supports the sustainable dissemination of its educational outcomes.

A first concrete use case of this openly available material will be the **SPEARHEAD** summer school planned to take place at the Christian-Albrechts-University Kiel (**CAU**) in fall 2026 (<https://spearhead-he.eu/school-workshop-3/>). The teaching activities of this summer school are intended to build directly upon the course materials provided here, demonstrating their practical applicability and serving as a foundation for future educational initiatives.

Bibliography

Gieseler, J., Afanasiev, A., Dumbovic, M., et al. 2025, High-Energy Particles in the Heliosphere, Zenodo, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.17951403](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17951403)